

TACTICS FOR CARRYING WOMEN AT HIGH RISK OF RECURRENT MISCARRIAGE

Rajabova Oygul Islomovna

Asian International University.

oygul.islomovna.1997@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13982730>

Abstract. This article covers the correct diagnosis and management of women at high risk of recurrent miscarriage.

Key words: pregnancy, menstrual period, spontaneous abortion, reproductive system, hyperandrogenism, thyroid dysfunction, infectious, steroid hormones, basal temperature.

ТАКТИКА ВЫНАШИВАНИЯ У ЖЕНЩИН С ВЫСОКИМ РИСКОМ ПРИВЫЧНОГО НЕВЫНАШИВАНИЯ БЕРЕМЕННОСТИ

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются вопросы правильной диагностики и ведения женщин с высоким риском привычного невынашивания беременности.

Ключевые слова: беременность, менструальный цикл, самопроизвольный аборт, репродуктивная система, гиперандрогения, дисфункция щитовидной железы, инфекционные, стероидные гормоны, базальная температура.

Relevance: One of the first places among the most important problems of practical obstetrics is the problem of miscarriage. Miscarriage is the spontaneous termination of pregnancy between conception and 37 weeks, counting from the first day of the last menstrual period.

Termination of pregnancy between conception and 22 weeks is called spontaneous abortion (miscarriage). A recurrent miscarriage is a spontaneous termination of pregnancy two or more times in a row. Every fourth wanted pregnancy ends in spontaneous miscarriage. The frequency of recurrent miscarriage is 0.6–2.3%. Recurrent miscarriage is a polyetiological complication of pregnancy, which is based on dysfunction of the reproductive system.

In the structure of habitual pregnancy losses, there are anatomical (they cause, according to various sources, 15% of all cases of miscarriage), endocrine (luteal phase insufficiency (LPF) of any origin, hyperandrogenism, thyroid dysfunction, diabetes mellitus, etc.), infectious, genetic and immunological factors. Timely identification of risk groups contributes to the formation of tactics for managing a woman during pregnancy.

Purpose of the study: Optimization of preconception preparation and treatment of miscarriage in women with recurrent pregnancy loss syndrome.

Materials and methods of research: At the Regional Perinatal Center in Bukhara, 70 women were examined at 6-12 weeks of pregnancy.

The women were divided into 2 groups: the main group consisted of 50 women with recurrent pregnancy loss syndrome and threatened miscarriage at the time of the examination, the control group included 20 women without RPL.

We conducted a comparative assessment of clinical and anamnestic data, functional research methods (basal temperature control) and significant laboratory parameters (determination of gonadotropic and steroid hormones in the blood (LH, FSH, T, E2, progesterone, DHEA-S, cortisol, TSH, free T3 and T4, AMH) on days 3-5 of phase I of the menstrual cycle). Ultrasound examination: on days 5-7 of the menstrual cycle and days 11,13,15 (folliculometry).

Results and discussions: clinical and anamnestic data showed that the total number of births in the control group was 6 term births, in the main group - 5, 2 term births and 3 premature births, the total number of abortions in women of the main group was 124 of which 3 were medical abortions, and 121 are early spontaneous abortions, while in the control group there are only 4 medical abortions.

The results of measuring basal temperature as the most informative test of functional diagnostics, confirming the presence of ovulation and the full functioning of the corpus luteum, indicated that women in the main group had disturbances in the regulation of the menstrual cycle before treatment.

Next, we carried out laboratory tests. The results of which showed that in women of the main group before treatment, testosterone levels (4.8) and the LH/FSH ratio (2.5) were high, and in the control group they were within normal limits. The average endometrial thickness in women of the main group before treatment on days 6-8 was 5.4 mm, on days 13-16 - 6.6 mm, on days 21-23 - 9.4 mm, which indicates that the endometrium is not ready for implantation.

After a complete examination and identification of existing disorders (3 menstrual cycles), treatment and preconception preparation were carried out for women with recurrent pregnancy loss syndrome.

The results after the treatment showed that the disorders were eliminated; according to the measurement of basal temperature, the duration of the secretory phase and the thickness of the endometrium (on days 13-16 - 11.1 mm, on days 21-23 - 12.2 mm) by the end of the menstrual cycle became sufficient for implantation and pregnancy maintenance.

Conclusions: In the history of women with SPPB, there is a high proportion of inflammatory diseases of the reproductive system, in particular inflammatory diseases of the

cervix in 21 patients (42%) in the main group and oopharitis in 16 (32%) and 2 (10%) in the control group.

All women with SPPB with absence of ovulation also had relative endometrial hypoplasia.

The use of estrogens in pre-gestational preparation over three menstrual cycles makes it possible to restore the normal thickness of the endometrium and ensure subsequent successful pregnancy in cases of NLF.

The main goal of preconception preparation, which is necessary for absolutely all women of reproductive age, is to plan pregnancy during the period of best readiness to conceive and carry a pregnancy to term. Preconception assessment of risk factors and their timely correction is the main condition for preventing obstetric and perinatal complications.

REFERENCES

1. Rajabova Oygul Islomovna.(2024). VIRUSLI GEPATITLAR VA TUG‘RUQDAN KEYINGI ERTA QON KETISHLARNI KAMAYTIRISHNING YANGI TEXNOLOGIYALARI. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 39(5), 99–106. <https://www.newjournal.org/index.php/01/article/view/11723>
2. Rajabova Oygul Islomovna .(2024). A Comparative Analysis of the Effectiveness of Vaginal Progesterone, Cervical Pesar, and Their Combination for Preventing the Risk of Premature Labor in High-Risk Pregnant Women BEST JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN SCIENCE, RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT, 3(3), 440-446. <http://www.bjisrd.com/index.php/bjisrd/article/view/1849/1700>
3. Rajabova Oygul Islomovna.(2024). MODERN CONCEPT OF RECURRENT VAGINAL INFECTIONS IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE, 3(04), 128-131. <https://jhlsr.innovascience.uz/index.php/jhlsr/article/view/518/455>
4. Rajabova Oygul Islomovna.(2024). METHODS OF PHARMACOTHERAPEUTIC TREATMENT OF ABNORMAL UTERINE BLEEDING IN GIRLS, 3(5),193-197 <https://mudarrisziyo.uz/index.php/pedagogika/article/view/945>
5. Rajabova Oygul Islomovna.(2024). Method Stopping Atonic Bleeding From the Uterus after Childbirth Using Balloon Tamponade International Journal of Alternative and Contemporary Therapy with U.S. ISSN 2995-5378 In Volume 2, Issue 9 (2024) <https://medicaljournals.eu/index.php/IJACT/article/view/965>
6. Farida Farkhodovna, K, Umida Rakhmatulloevna, N, & Mokhigul Abdurasulovna, B. (2022). ETIOLOGY OF CHRONIC RHINOSINUSITIS AND EFFECTIVENESS OF ETIOTROPIC TREATMENT METHODS (LITERATURE REVIEW). Новости образования:

исследование в XXI веке, 1(4), 377–381. извлечено от

<https://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/noiv/article/view/1367>

7. Numonova, A., & Narzulaeva, U. (2023). EPIDEMIOLOGY AND ETIOPATHOGENESIS OF CHF. Наука и инновация, 1(15), 115-119.
8. Орипова Озода Олимовна, Самиева Гулноза Уткуровна, Хамидова Фариди Муиновна, & Нарзулаева Умида Рахматуллаевна (2020). Состояние плотности распределения лимфоидных клеток слизистой оболочки гортани и проявления местного иммунитета при хроническом ларингите (анализ секционного материала). Academy, (4 (55)), 83-86.
9. Umida Rakhmatulloevna Narzulaeva, & Xamrayeva Muxlisa Farmon qizi. (2023). ETIOPATHOGENESIS OF HEMOLYTIC ANEMIA. Web of Medicine: Journal of Medicine, Practice and Nursing, 1(1), 1–4. Retrieved from <https://webofjournals.com/index.php/5/article/view/26>
10. Нарзулаева, У., Самиева, Г., & Насирова, Ш. (2023). Гемореологические нарушения на ранних стадиях гипертензии в жарком климате. Журнал биомедицины и практики, 1(1), 221–225. <https://doi.org/10.26739/2181-9300-2021-1-31>
11. Umida Rakhmatulloevna Narzulaeva. (2023). Important Aspects of Etiology And Pathogenesis of Hemolytic Anemias. American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149), 1(7), 179–182. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJPMHS/article/view/817>
12. Нарзулаева, У. Р., Самиева, Г. У., & Насирова, Ш. Ш. (2021). ИССИҚ ИҚЛИМДА КЕЧУВЧИ ГИПЕРТОНИЯ КАСАЛЛИГИНИНГ БОШЛАНҒИЧ БОСҚИЧЛАРИДА ГЕМОРЕОЛОГИК БУЗИЛИШЛАР. ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ, 6(1).
13. Нарзулаева, У., Самиева, Г., Лапасова, З., & Таирова, С. (2023). Значение диеты в лечении артериальной гипертензии . Журнал биомедицины и практики, 1(3/2), 111–116. <https://doi.org/10.26739/2181-9300-2021-3-98>
14. Narzulaeva Umida Rakhmatulloevna, Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna, & Ismatova Marguba Shaukatovna (2020). SPECIFICITY OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF THE INITIAL STAGES OF HYPERTENSION IN ARID ZONES OF UZBEKISTAN AND NON-DRUG APPROACHES TO TREATMENT. Кронос, (4 (43)), 15-17.
15. Umida Raxmatulloevna Narzulaeva, & Mohigul Abdurasulovna Bekkulova (2023). Arterial gipertenziya etiologiyasida dislipidemiyaning xavf omili sifatidagi roli. Science and Education, 4 (2), 415-419.

16. Narzulaeva, U. R., & Samieva, G. U. (2021). Nasirova ShSh. Hemoreological Disorders in The Early Stages Of Hypertension In Hot Climates. *Journal of Biomedicine and Practice*, 6(1), 221-225.
17. Dilsora Nuriddinovna Juraeva, Umida Rakhmatulloevna Narzulaeva, & Kurbonova Gulbahor Aslamovna. (2022). GENDER DIFFERENCES IN THE PARACLINICAL FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF TRIGEMINAL NEURALGIA. *World Bulletin of Public Health*, 8, 186-190. Retrieved from <https://www.scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbph/article/view/751>
18. Narzulaeva, U. (2023). PATHOGENETIC MECHANISMS OF MICROCIRCULATION DISORDERS. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(10), 60–65. Retrieved from <https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibmscr/article/view/2811>
19. Narzulaeva Umida Rakhmatulloevna and Rakhmatova Fotima Ulugbekovna, “PATHOGENETIC MECHANISMS OF DISORDERS IN THE HEMOSTASIS SYSTEM OBSERVED IN PATIENTS INFECTED WITH COVID-19”, *IEJRD - International Multidisciplinary Journal*, vol. 7, no. ICMEI, p. 3, Feb. 2023.
20. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ЛИЦ ЗЛОУПОТРЕБЛЯЮЩЕЕСЯ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИМИ НАПИТКАМИ. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 3-15.
21. Nematilloevna, X. M., & Salohiddinovna, X. Y. (2024). LOTIN TILI VA TIBBIYOT TERMINOLOGIYASINI O'QITISHDA TALABALARDA MOTIVATSIYANI KUCHAYTIRISH YO'LLARI. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 38-48.
22. Nematilloevna, X. M., & Salohiddinovna, X. Y. (2024). LOTIN TILI SIFATLARI VA DARAJALARI YASALISHINING MUHIM XUSUSIYATLARI. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 16-26.
23. Nematilloevna, X. M., & Salohiddinovna, X. Y. (2024). FARMATSEVTIKADA DORI PREPARATLARI NOMLARIDA MA'NOLI BO'LAKLARNING QO'LLANILISHI. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 49-59.
24. Xalimova, Y. S. (2024). Morphology of the Testes in the Detection of Infertility. *Journal of Science in Medicine and Life*, 2(6), 83-88.
25. Хафизова, М. Н., & Халимова, Ю. С. (2024). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ЧАСТОТНЫХ ОТРЕЗКОВ В НАИМЕНОВАНИЯХ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННЫХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ В ФАРМАЦЕВТИКЕ. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 310-321.
26. Хафизова, М. Н., & Халимова, Ю. С. (2024). МОТИВАЦИОННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ ЛАТЫНИ И МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 299-309.

27. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). ОСОБЕННОСТИ СОЗРЕВАНИЕ И ФУНКЦИОНИРОВАНИЕ ЯИЧНИКОВ. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 337-347.
28. Saloxiddinovna, X. Y., & Ne'matillaevna, X. M. (2024). FEATURES OF THE STRUCTURE OF THE REPRODUCTIVE ORGANS OF THE FEMALE BODY. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 322-336.
29. Nematilloevna, X. M., & Salohiddinovna, X. Y. (2024). LOTIN PREFIKSLARI ANATOMIK TERMINLAR YASALISHIDA ASOSIY KOMPONENT SIFATIDA. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 27-37.
30. Qilichovna, A. M., & Nematilloevna, X. M. (2024). METABOLIK SINDROMI VA QON BOSIMI BOR BEMORLARDA O'ZGARISH XUSUSIYATLARI BAHOLASH: Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari. *Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari*, 6(4), 187-196.
31. Qilichovna, A. M., & Nematilloevna, X. M. (2024). TIBBIYOT TILI HISOBLANMISH LOTIN TILINI SAMARALI O'RGANISH OMILLARI: Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari. *Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari*, 6(4), 197-206.
32. Tog'aydullayeva, D. D. (2024). Embrional Davrda Gemopoez Va Unda Jigar Va Taloqning Roli. *Journal of Science in Medicine and Life*, 2(6), 132-134.
33. Tog'aydullayeva, D. D. (2024). Occurrence of Combination Diseases in Ischemic Heart Disease and Metabolic Syndrome and their Diagnosis. *Journal of Science in Medicine and Life*, 2(6), 126-131.
34. Tog'aydullayeva, D. D. (2024). Occurrence of Combination Diseases in Ischemic Heart Disease and Metabolic Syndrome and their Diagnosis. *Journal of Science in Medicine and Life*, 2(6), 126-131.